

3-Substituted-6-aryl-7-thioaryloxy-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines and their corresponding Sulphones as Potential Antimicrobial and Antiparasitic Derivatives

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Antiparasitic activity of some derivatives of triazoles is well-known¹. In continuation of our work on fused ring *s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazines^{2,3}, a new series of potential antimicrobial and antiparasitic agents have been prepared. The compounds of interest, viz. 3-substituted-6-aryl-7-thioaryloxy-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazines (3) and their corresponding sulphones (4) (Scheme 1) were selected to contain various substituents according to the Topliss Scheme⁴.

- 3,4a : R = CH₃, R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl
 b : R = C₂H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl
 c : R = C₆H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl
 d : R = *p*-CH₃-C₆H₄, R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl
 e : R = R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H
 f : R = C₂H₅, R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H
 g : R = C₆H₅, R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H
 h : R = *p*-Cl-C₆H₄, R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H
 i : R = 4'-Pyridyl, R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H
 j : R = C₂H₅, R₁ = R₂ = H
 k : R = C₆H₅, R₁ = R₂ = H
 l : R = CH₃, R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H
 m : R = C₂H₅, R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H
 n : R = C₆H₅, R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H
 o : R = *p*-Cl-C₆H₄, R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H

Scheme 1

The starting compounds 3-substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-(4H)-1,2,4-triazoles (1), earlier reported⁵ were prepared by a modified method². Compounds 1 were then condensed with 2-bromo-2-thioaryloxyacetophenones to give the sulphides (3a-o). Compounds 2 were prepared by photobrominating 2-thioaryloxyacetophenones⁷. Compounds 3 were conveniently oxidised to the corresponding sulphones (4) with H₂O₂ in the presence of acetic acid. On refluxing molar quantities of 3-ethyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-(4H)-triazole (1; R = C₂H₅), 2-bromo-2-thioaryloxyacetophenone (2, R₁ = R₂ = H) and pyridine in ethanol for 3 h, 3j was obtained. Its ir spectrum showed absorbance due to fused *s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazines ring system at 2 900, 1 565, 1 450, 1 315, 1 090, 880 and 785 cm⁻¹. The absence of carbonyl frequency indicated closed fused *s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazines system. This was further confirmed by the pmr analysis which showed a multiplet (10H) at δ 8.0-7.3, singlet (1H) at 5.5 due to C-H at 7-position, a quartet (2H) at 2.68 and a triplet (3H) at 1.40 due to C₂H₅ protons at position-3. The cmr spectra of this compound showed signals due to 18 carbon atoms. It showed signals for imino carbons at 142.58, 150.14 and 154.45, a multiplet for aromatic carbons at 136.0-126.0, a methyne carbon at 45.04, the methyl and methylene carbons at 10.83 and 21.54 respectively. Compound 3j was further converted by oxidation with 30% hydrogen peroxide to its corresponding sulphone (4j). Its ir spectrum showed strong characteristic absorption peaks at 1 350 and 1 180 cm⁻¹ due to asymmetric and symmetric SO₂ stretching mode⁶. In the similar way other derivatives of 3 and 4 were synthesised.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian-300S (300 MHz) and Bruker WH-270Hz (67.89 MHz) spectrometers respectively.

2-Bromo-2-thioaryloxyacetophenones (2). General procedure: 2-Thioaryloxyacetophenones⁷ (0.1 mol) taken in CHCl₃ or CS₂ (30 ml), was brominated by the dropwise addition of liquid bromine

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(5.16 ml, 0.1 mol) for 10–15 min in presence of uv-light (generated from a Philips HPR 125W lamp; 315–400 nm); temperature of the reaction was maintained at 10–20° with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was then washed with aqueous NaHCO₃ (10%) followed by water, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol.

2-Alkyl/Aryl-6-aryl-7-thioaryloxy-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines (3a–o). *General procedure:* A mixture of compounds **2** (0.01 mol), **1** (0.01 mol) and pyridine (1.2 ml, 0.015 mol) in absolute alcohol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. Alcohol was then distilled under reduced pressure and the reaction mixture poured in cold dilute HCl. A gummy product that separated out was washed with aqueous 10% NaHCO₃ solution and water, and crystallised in ethanol (yields 64–81%): **3a** (81%), m.p. 178°; **3b** (81%), m.p. 160°, ν_{\max} 2 900, 1 565, 1 520, 1 450, 1 315, 1 085, 880, 825, 790 cm⁻¹, ¹H nmr (270 MHz) δ 8.00–7.2 ν (9H, m, ArH), 5.43 (1H, s, CH), 2.68 (2H, q, CH₂), 1.35 (3H, t, CH₃); ¹H nmr (60 MHz) δ 8.00–7.40 (10H, m, ArH), 5.50 (1H, s, CH), 2.68 (2H, q, CH₂), 1.40 (3H, t, CH₃); **3c**, m.p. 183°; **d**, 208°; **e**, 203°; **f**, 201°; **g**, 189°; **h**, 220°; **i**, 210°; **j**, 198°; **k**, 155°; **l**, 204°; **m**, 188°; **n**, 208°; **o**, 210°.

3-Alkyl/Aryl-6-aryl-7-arylsulphonyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines (4): **3** (0.5 g) was treated with concentrated H₂SO₄ (2–3 ml) in cold. It was left for 15 min and glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was then added at 15°, followed by H₂O₂ (2 ml, 30%). The mixture was then cooled and set aside for 24 h. A little H₂O₂ was then added and the mixture was further left for 12 h. A crystalline compound separates out, which was washed with aqueous NaHCO₃ (10%) and water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (yields 80–88%): **4a** (86%), m.p. 195°; **4b** (85%), m.p. 188°, ν_{\max} 2 900, 1 565, 1 520, 1 450, 1 340, 1 180, 1 085, 880, 825, 790 cm⁻¹; **4c**, m.p. 198°; **d**, 221°; **e**, 238°; **f**, 223°; **g**, 211°; **h**, 224°; **i**, 246°; **j**, 216°; **k**, 187°; **l**, 228°; **m**, 210°; **n**, 230°; **o**, 222°.

Antimicrobial activity: Compounds **3** and **4** were screened for their antimicrobial activity by employing Ditch-Plate Technique⁸ at a concentration of 5 mg cm⁻³ and tested against *S. aureus*,

E. coli, *S. typhosa*, *S. para.*, *C. albicans* and *S. marcescens*. In case of **3**, total inhibition of the growth was observed for *S. aureus* in **3a**, **b**, **h**, **l**, **m** and **o**, for *E. coli* in **3b**, **d**, **g** and **m**, for *S. typhosa* in **3a**, **c**, **f**, **h** and **m** for *S. marcescens* in **3b**, **k**, **l** and **n**. Compounds **4** were more active than **3**.

Anthelmintic activity: Compounds **3** and **4** were screened for their anthelmintic activity⁹ using *Hymenylpsis nana*, *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* and *Ancylostoma cyelandicum*. The study was conducted at a concentration of 1 mg cm⁻³ at which either paralysis or death of the parasites was observed. Compounds **4** were inactive at a higher dose even after 24 h. Compounds **3** showed moderate activity; **3b**, **c**, **e**, **h**, **k** and **o** were active against *H. nana* **3a**, **b**, **h**, **k** and **n** active against *N. brasiliensis* and **3b**, **d**, **i**, **m** and **n** against *A. cyelandicum*.

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